

EFFECTIVENESS OF PHYSIOTHERAPY IN RESTORATION OF JOINT FUNCTION IN OSTEOARTHRITIS

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Summary : Physiotherapy and therapeutic physical training methods recommended by us to patients were used in the article. The results before and after the treatments were compared. The general assessment of the results of the treatment of arthrosis of different severity was determined by comparing the indicators before and after the treatments.

Key words: coxarthrosis, gonarthrosis, obesity, knee joint, osteoarthrosis, rehabilitation, osteophytes, quality of life, disability.

Relevance. Currently, the consequences of injuries and diseases of the musculoskeletal system remain of great social importance. Osteoarthritis accounts for 55% of all orthopedic diseases, one third of which affects the knee joint, reaching 33.3% of cases.

Literature data show that osteoarthritis is the most common pathology among joint diseases. This disease occurs in 10 to 16% of the world's population, and is observed in almost everyone over the age of 70 [2,9].

Osteoarthritis is a clinical syndrome characterized by joint pain, which is associated with functional impairment and reduced quality of life. OA is a common cause of disability worldwide and is associated with a high incidence of pain. In general, the main goal of treatment for patients with OA is to limit the progression of the disease, while rehabilitation, which is necessary for almost all patients after the exacerbation of the pathological process, is to reduce pain, restore functional ability, and improve the quality of life of patients [1,5].

OA support-movement e ng among system diseases wide widespread from diseases Risk factors for OA include: hereditary (40-60% of patients have relatives with OA); constitutional factors (age, female gender, obesity, high bone density); local factors (joint injuries, decreased muscle strength, abnormal joint mobility). In many cases, several factors are observed together.

In the pathological process of osteoarthritis, with the development of degenerative-dystrophic processes, not only the articular cartilage is damaged, with fibrillation, cracks, scarring, and ultimately complete loss of the cartilage, but primarily the subchondral bone, ligaments, capsule, synovial membrane, and periarticular muscles are damaged.

Objective: To study the dynamics of outcomes with important features characterizing the course of the disease in order to develop rehabilitation methods and measures to improve the quality of life of patients with osteoarthritis . The aim of the study was to evaluate the results of treatment of patients with this pathology after the recommended rehabilitation.

Materials and methods. Clinical research was conducted in the traumatology and physiotherapy departments of the Bukhara Regional Multidisciplinary Medical Center. Examination and treatment were carried out between 2019 and 2021. Male and female patients aged 35 to 65 years with a diagnosis of osteoarthritis were involved in the research with their consent. Of these, 89 (66.9%) patients were diagnosed with knee arthrosis (gonarthrosis) (code M17, class XIII, ICD-10), and 44 (33.1%) with a diagnosis of coxarthrosis (code M16, class XIII, ICD-10).

The main group of patients with OA underwent physical exercises (Scandinavian walking, butterfly position, exercises that improve joint mobility) along with physiotherapy. The nature and order of the recommended therapeutic exercises were selected individually. One course of treatment consisted of 12 exercises, performed for 30 minutes daily. Therapeutic exercises were recommended from the 3rd day of treatment. Therapeutic exercises in osteoarthritis

were performed in a sitting and lying position, depending on the nature of the pain in the joints, with an individual approach, gradually increasing the range of motion. Sharp movements and exercises that could cause severe pain were not performed. The main principle that the patient should follow when performing therapeutic exercises is the regularity and gradualness of the exercises. The patient's heart rate was taken into account in each session. Heart rate during exercise and at rest was determined.

Results. As a result of rehabilitation methods in patients with osteoarthritis, their condition improved, manifested by a decrease in swelling of the periarticular tissues ($p < 0.05$). The dynamics of joint parameters in patients with OA are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Clinical and radiological changes in the joint

Group	I (n=103)	II (n=100)	I (n=103)	II (n=100)
<i>Signs</i>	<i>Before treatment</i>		<i>After treatment</i>	
movement is limited	3.06±1.51	1.53 ± 0.10	0.86 ±0.07	1.33 ± 0.10
cramps in the joint	0.76 ± 0.04	0.83 ± 0.07	0.35 ±0.05	0.77 ± 0.08
deformation	2, 35 ±1,16	1.30 ± 0.12	1.02 ±0.07	1.17 ± 0.11
work	0.49 ± 0.05	0.67 ± 0.09	0.11 ±0.03	0.43 ± 0.09

Studying the dynamics of clinical indicators of patients with OA undergoing rehabilitation treatment (main group, n=103) and (comparison group, n=100)

revealed significant differences in the clinical signs of the disease after the course.

While patients in the main group showed significant ($p < 0.05$) improvement in all clinical parameters , patients in the comparison group did not show any significant changes in the studied parameters. In particular, in the observation group, a significant improvement in joint stiffness and swelling index was observed, which was not observed in patients in the comparison group.

Table 2

Dynamics of clinical indicators in patients with OA, in points (before and after treatment)

Clinical signs	Group I	Group II
Your scale	6.36±0.16*	5.23±0.32*
	1.84±0.11*	4.17±0.23*
Leken index	6.53±0.17*	7.27±0.27
	4.92±0.14*	6.7±0.23
Evening pain intensity	1.30 ±0.06*	1.57 ±0.11
	0.86 ±0.05*	1.43 ±0.11
Morning sickness	1.23 ±0.05 *	1.40 ±0.09
	0.93±0.05*	1.23±0.09

* Difference between pre- and post-treatment parameters $p < 0.05$.

According to the indicators presented in Table 2, when comparing the results before and after treatment in the main group, a decrease in the intensity of pain in the joints according to the VASH scale (from 6.36 ± 0.16 to 1.84 ± 0.11), an improvement in the functional state of the joints according to the Leken index (from 6.53 ± 0.17 to It is seen that there was a positive change in the intensity of evening pain (from 1.30 ± 0.06 to 0.86 ± 0.05), morning stiffness (from 1.23 ± 0.05 to 0.93 ± 0.05). In the comparison group, only the VASH scale indicators had a significance level of $p < 0.05$.

According to the data of the Kellgren-Lawrence knee joint radiological

examination of the patients in the main group, there were more grade II changes, while according to the data of the radiological examinations of the patients in the comparison group, grade II and III signs gave the same indicators.

In the treatment of patients with OA, the main group of patients was recommended, along with physiotherapy treatments, therapeutic exercises specially selected by us.

In the comparison group, the average duration of the treatment course was 10-12 days, and a positive clinical result was achieved within 18-20 weeks. In the main group, the average duration of the treatment course was also 10-12 days, and clinical efficacy was observed for an average of 24-25 weeks. The combined use of electrophoresis with caripain and laser in patients with osteoarthritis has shown high efficiency and pathogenetically based treatment. When electrophoresis is used with caripain, a depot of enzymes is formed under the skin in the area of the pathological process, and the therapeutic effect lasts for 2-3 weeks after the end of the treatment. Laser therapy is considered a highly effective treatment method for various orthopedic disorders, which leads to a reduction in the duration of the treatment course due to improved metabolism in the affected area, increased tissue and vascular regeneration.

As a result of physiotherapy and therapeutic exercises recommended for patients with OA, the patients' condition improved positively. This was manifested in a decrease in swelling of the periarticular tissues and a decrease in pain, which resulted in a significant change in the range of motion of the joints when examined by goniometry ($p < 0.05$).

The dynamics of joint motion changes were measured by goniometry every 3, 6, and 12 months. The dynamics of joint motion in patients with OA are presented in Table 3.3.

Table 3

Dynamics of changes in joint motion in patients with OA (joint flexion

and extension, in degrees)

Patient group	Before treatment	After treatment		
		In 3 months	In 6 months	In 12 months
Group I	105.54±1.	103.50±1.	98.19±1.5	89.87±1.2
	17	14	3	3
	161.54±0.	162.20±0.	168.16±0.	173.25±0.
	64	66	57	34
Group II	103.17±2.	101.50±2.	100.00±2.	99.20±2.5
	88	80	62	8
	158.83±0.	159.33±0.	160.43±1.	161.03±1.
	92	92	07	11

The results in the table showed that only physiotherapeutic procedures were recommended to the patients of the comparison group, so the changes in them were lower than the results of the first group of patients.

In patients with OA, after the rehabilitation course, the increase in the range of motion in the joint in the main group was significantly greater than in the comparison group. After 3, 6, and 12 months, the amplitude of flexion movements in the joint in the main group under the influence of the rehabilitation course was on average: $2.04 \pm 1.2^\circ$; $7.35 \pm 1.4^\circ$; $15.67 \pm 1.2^\circ$ ($p < 0.05$). The indicators in the comparison group changed as follows: $1.67 \pm 2.8^\circ$; $3.17 \pm 2.8^\circ$; $3.97 \pm 2.7^\circ$. The amplitude of flexion movements in the joint in patients was $-0.66 \pm 0.6^\circ$; $-6.62 \pm 0.6^\circ$; $-11.71 \pm 0.5^\circ$ ($p < 0.05$). When we analyzed such indicators in the comparison group, we got the following results: $-0.50 \pm 0.9^\circ$; $-1.60 \pm 1.0^\circ$; $-2.2 \pm 1.1^\circ$. The increase in the amplitude of joint movement in the patients of the main group was significantly different from the patients in the comparison group: $2.0 \pm 1.9^\circ$; $2.87 \pm 0.8^\circ$; $-1.81 \pm 2.1^\circ$; $7.73 \pm 0.8^\circ$; $-9.33 \pm 1.9^\circ$; $12.22 \pm 0.7^\circ$ ($p < 0.05$).

Table 4

Evaluation of ultrasound examination of joints

Indicators	Before treatment		After treatment	
	Group I	Group II	Group I	Group II
Joint inside fluid (synovitis)	0.98±0.0 5	1.17±0.1 1	0.93±0.0 5	0.83±0.0 8
Osteophyte	1.23±0.0 6	1.60±0.1 0	1.13±0.0 5	1.23±0.1 1
What is it?	0.22±0.0 4	0.27±0.0 8	0.22±0.0 4	0.33±0.0 9
Joint pain	0.83±0.0 4	0.79±0.0 7	0.73±0.0 4	1.70±0.0 9

Difference between indicators before and after treatment ($p < 0.05$).

From the indicators in table 4, it can be seen that the degree of changes in the pathological processes in the joints was determined by the method of ultrasound examination of the joints. It was found that the indicators of intra-articular fluid in the patients of the main group changed in a positive direction compared to the comparison group. The joint fracture procedure also resulted in higher scores in our main group compared to the comparison group.

Conclusion: Thus, the rehabilitation course of treatment in patients with osteoarthritis led to a significant improvement in the static and dynamic mobility of the affected joints.

Also, rehabilitation of patients with OA leads to a more pronounced improvement in clinical indicators, electrophoresis treatment with caripain led to a reduction in pain syndrome, a significant change in indicators in a positive direction. Along with morning stiffness and improvement in joint function, it allowed and was recommended to patients.

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